

OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE COMPANY IN THE PANDEMIC AND POST PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

Purpose – The aim of the research paper is to conduct a case study on how a construction company reconfigured its business based on the opportunities generated by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology/approach - The research methodology applied in the paper comprises theoretical and applied research methods and techniques, implemented through the bibliographic and case study method.

Findings – Using SWOT analysis as a strategic planning tool, the management team “took advantage” of the challenges of the COVID-19 crisis, managing to adapt to the needs of the population during this period and bringing the company significant increases in turnover and profit during the pandemic and post-pandemic period.

Research limitations/implications – The management tools presented in the paper can be used by the managers to inform managerial decisions, both in setting short-term objectives and in planning long-term development strategies.

Practical implications – The case study has a high degree of practical involvement, based on practical management tools used in the company and analysis of economic and financial indicators.

Originality/value – The originality of the paper lies in its analysis of how society has benefited from the opportunities of the pandemic and post-pandemic period.

Key words: post-pandemic, opportunities, management.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has created a global crisis that impacts every individual, institution and organization. The Covid-19 crisis has had a strong impact on the medical, social and especially the economic environment worldwide. The economic impact was not caused by the pandemic itself, but by global measures taken to control the pandemic.

Although the impact of the COVID-19 crisis is now being felt in the post-pandemic period and is having a negative effect on the economy, there are companies that have found opportunities for business development in the post-pandemic period.

References in text

Crises affect private companies as well as public and administrative institutions, causing changes in their evolution. The issue of crises thus require a detailed analysis of how companies use specific methods of crisis management and substantiation of a decision in times of crisis. (Manciu, et all, 2016a)

The quality of the decisions and their substantiation in times of crisis plays a decisive role in the trajectory of the companies. Getting businesses through periods of crisis means maintaining economic performance through the management methods and techniques used in decision-making. (Manciu, et all, 2016b)

The disaster theory literature points out that financial issues and physical resources allow small firms to be more resilient during crises. (Belitski, et al, 2021).

Opportunities in the pandemic period

The COVID-19 pandemic started at the end of 2019 worldwide and in Romania at the beginning of 2020. During the pandemic, a number of restrictions and health protection measures were imposed, which were opportunities that Atlas Sport's management team took advantage of both during the pandemic and post-pandemic period.

Using management tools such as SWOT analysis and relying on the resources already existing in the company: specialised sales staff, suppliers, transport network, access to e-procurement system, etc., the management team understood the opportunity generated by the pandemic, the need for protective equipment, and made the optimal decision to develop a new department in the company to maintain or increase the level of managerial performance during the pandemic.

Atlas Sport has kept its core business sports construction, but the new medical equipment supply business is perfectly in line with the health protection requirements generated by the restrictions imposed during the pandemic period, which brought the company a considerable evolution of its financial indicators in the first year of the pandemic.

In order to better understand how the management team based its decision to create a new department and choose a new business area we have reproduced below the SWOT analysis, which is “a key tool used by businesses for strategic planning” (Benzaghta, et al, 2021).

“The objective of a SWOT analysis is to use the knowledge an enterprise has about its internal and external environments and formulate its strategy accordingly” (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015), thus in formulating the objective to enter the new market, the management team carefully analysed its internal environment, with strengths beneficial to achieving the strategy, being helped by the immense opportunities in the external environment generated by the evolution of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 1. SWOT analysis of the ATLAS SPORT SRL company during the pandemic period

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Existence of a department specialised in direct sales (Business to Business, Business to Government, Business-to-Consumer) ✓ Existence of a department specialised in public tenders and use of SICAP (E-procurement system) ✓ Existence of a database with a large number of public institutions in Romania (town halls, schools and high schools, etc.) ✓ Existent connections with the suppliers in China (the main exporter of health protection products) ✓ Knowledge of the transport networks China - Romania ✓ Knowledge of import conditions and customs procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of experience in selling medical and protection equipment - Lack of technical knowledge in the medical field - Lack of contact details for beneficiaries of medical equipment - Lack of authorisations and approvals required for the supply of medical equipment
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Introduction of restrictions and health protection measures in all institutions and public places as a result of the COVID pandemic ✓ Increased level of health protection in all health facilities following the evolution of the COVID-19 pandemic ✓ Sharp increase in demand for health protection products ✓ Rising prices in the health protection equipment market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production shutdown in many parts of China (the main exporter of medical and health protection products) due to the COVID-19 pandemic - Congestion on the China-Romania sea route and delays in product deliveries - Medium to long term uncertainty based on the uncertainty of the evolution of the COVID pandemic

Along with the restrictions generated by the COVID-19 pandemic, a series of health protection measures were regulated in all public places in Romania, as well as increased protection in medical institutions, which generated a sharp increase in demand for medical products and health protection on the market. These are the main opportunities generated by the pandemic that Atlas Sport SRL has capitalised on during the pandemic period, relying on its strengths, namely specialised sales and tendering departments, suppliers, transport networks, access to the e-procurement system and the existence of a database of public institutions in Romania. Thus, in the midst of the pandemic crisis, the company reconfigured its business generating a significant increase in revenue in the first year of the pandemic.

Opportunities and threats during the post-pandemic period

At the end of 2020, the management team again made a significant strategic development decision to transform the newly created department at the onset of the pandemic into a stand-alone company. Thus Atlas Medical SRL, a supplier of medical protective equipment, medical devices and disinfectants, was created. Thus, the “reshaping” during the pandemic was not temporary and became permanent in the post-pandemic reality.

Today, the weaknesses listed above have become strengths of the newly created society, based on the experience of the pandemic period. Thus, during the pandemic, the sales team built up experience in selling medical and protective equipment and gained technical knowledge in the medical field, created the necessary database of direct recipients of medical equipment and obtained the necessary authorisations and approvals to supply these types of products.

With the end of the pandemic, the threats presented earlier in the SWOT analysis have almost completely disappeared and in the post-pandemic reality have been replaced by the existence of competition, the entry into a period of economic recession as a result of the pandemic crisis and the war in Ukraine.

The post-pandemic opportunities that the newly created company can benefit from, given its strengths, are represented by the continued need to develop and modernise the medical infrastructure in Romania.

Table 2. SWOT analysis of the ATLAS MEDICAL SRL company during the post-pandemic period

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The existence of a department specialised in direct sales (Business to Business, Business to Government, Business-to-Consumer) and public tenders and the use of SICAP (E-procurement system) ✓ Existence of a customer database ✓ Existent connections with the suppliers in China (the main exporter of health protection products) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permanent need to improve technical knowledge in the medical field - Low market share as a new market entrant - The need for local suppliers to shorten delivery times
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Continuous need to develop and modernise the medical infrastructure in Romania 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - existence of competition, - entering a period of economic recession as a result of the pandemic crisis and the war in Ukraine

Analysis of economic and financial indicators

Atlas Sport SRL is a company operating in the field of construction, specialising in the construction and landscaping of sports fields and playgrounds for children. In this phase of the case study we present an analysis of the main economic indicators over the period 2014 - 2021, thus capturing their evolution both in the pre-pandemic and the pandemic period.

From the data presented above, there is a continuous increase in turnover since its establishment until 2020, when it recorded the highest value since its establishment, namely 43,439,710 RON. The graph above shows a dramatic decrease in turnover in 2021 compared to the previous year 2020, when turnover doubled compared to the previous year 2019.

Figure 1. The evolution of Atlas Sport's turnover in the period 2014-2021

Given that the medical equipment sales department was set up during 2020, an activity which in 2021 was transferred to Atlas Medical, for these two years we carried out a detailed analysis of the composition of turnover. Thus for the year 2020 we have broken down the income from the execution of works and the income from the sale of goods – medical products, and for the year 2021 we have added the turnover of the newly established company Atlas Medical.

Figure 2. Evolution of Atlas Sport's and Medical's cumulated turnover in the period 2014-2021

Breaking down revenue by structure, there is an increase in revenue from the execution of works in 2020 compared to the previous year, but the increase is only 44 percent. Taking into account the turnover achieved by Atlas Medical in 2021, we notice a decrease in the cumulated revenue of the two activities by 22 percent in 2021 compared to 2020.

In order to calculate the indicator Size of profit we have taken into account the data in the following table, expressed in RON:

Table 3. The net profit of the company Atlas Sport in the period 2014 – 2021

Year	Total Income	Total Expenses	Net Profit
2014	1,130,765	970,951	138,005
2015	3,274,756	2,435,364	707,736
2016	5,591,627	3,992,149	1,360,254
2017	11,918,662	9,648,686	1,940,033
2018	15,214,424	13,935,747	1,093,614
2019	20,225,670	16,222,269	3,445,592
2020	44,011,720	32,988,126	9,617,645
2021	32,153,743	28,723,026	3,012,314

The analysis carried out on the net profit recorded by Atlas Sport SRL in the period 2014 - 2020 shows a permanent evolution of it, with only one decrease in 2018 when the profit decreased by 44 percent compared to the previous year. This year's profit decrease was followed by significant increases in the following years, i.e. an increase of 3.15 times in 2019 compared to 2018, and in 2020 the company recorded the highest amount of profit, i.e. 9,617,645 RON, with an increase of 179 percent compared to the previous year. After this significant increase in 2020, the company registered in 2021 a huge decrease of profit, recording a value of only 31 percent of the value recorded in the previous year.

Figure 3. Comparative evolution income - expenses - profit in 2014 -2021 - Atlas Sport

Table 4. The inflation rates for the period 2014 -2021

Year	The inflation rates
2014	1.1
2015	-0.6
2016	-1.5
2017	1.3
2018	4.6
2019	3.8
2020	2.6
2021	5.1

Source: <https://insse.ro/cms/ro/content/ipc%E2%80%93serie-de-date-anuala>

The inflation rate must also be taken into account in determining the real profit of the company. The following table shows the inflation rates for the period 2014 -2021 taken from the National Institute of Statistics. (Table 4)

Using the previously calculated net profit and the annual inflation rate we calculate the real profit of the company using the following formula:

$$\text{Real profit} = \text{Net profit} - (\text{Net profit} \times \text{Inflation rate})$$

Figure 4. The evolution of Atlas Sport's real profit in the period 2014-2021

Given that the activity of selling medical protection products has been transferred to Atlas Medical, we also took into account the profit of 2,725,868 RON made by Atlas Medical in 2021. Thus, taking into account the values of the profit recorded on both companies, we obtain a total of 5,738,182 RON, representing 60 percent of the value of the profit made in 2020.

Figure 5. Evolution of Atlas Sport's and Medical's cumulated profit in the period 2014-2021

In order to calculate the financial return we will use the calculation formula:

$$\text{ROE} = (\text{PN} / \text{CPR}) \times 100.$$

Thus, for the calculation we take the value of net profit and equity from the financial statements.

Figure 6. Analysis of financial return in the period 2014 - 2021 at Atlas Sport SRL

"The financial rate of return – ROE – expresses the degree to which the firm's equity generates net profit" (Gomoi, 2021). The analysis shows a maximum financial rate of return recorded by Atlas Sport in 2016 of 94.11 percent, with the lowest financial rate of return of 21.20 percent recorded in 2021.

Another indicator we looked at is the average number of employees, an indicator that was continuously growing between 2014-2018. The maximum value of 74 employees was recorded in 2018, followed by a decrease in the number of employees, reaching an average of 50 employees in 2021.

Figure 7. Evolution of the average number of employees in the period 2014-2021

Discussion and conclusions

From the above analysis it appears that, although 2020 was the year in which the Covid pandemic started, for Atlas Sport SRL it was the best year from an economic and financial point of view, recording maximum turnover and profit values. The increase in the values of the indicators analysed is also due to revenues from the health protection equipment supply activity, a newly introduced activity in the company following the opportunities generated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The financial data show a dramatic drop in both turnover and net profit in 2021, but if we take into account the fact that the medical

equipment sales activity has been transferred to Atlas Medical and add up the figures of both companies, the drop in indicators is maintained, but the difference compared to the previous year is much smaller.

Thus, we can conclude that the opportunities generated by the pandemic period were beneficial for the company and the management team that knew how to take advantage of them, and that the changes during the pandemic became definitive in the post-pandemic reality. Atlas Medical continues to supply medical equipment with a development strategy based on the opportunities of the external environment and on the fact that the medical infrastructure in Romania needs development and modernisation.

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